

Coffee Marketing Strategy Using SWOT and QSPM Analysis: A Case Study

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Abstract:- Coffee is one of the the most popular drink in the world, including in Indonesia. Study this use SWOT analysis (Strength, Weakness, Threat, Opportunity) and and QSPM (*Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix*) to prioritize strategies and alternatives Priority marketing in implementation especially in the XYZ coffee business located in West Aceh Regency, Aceh, Indonesia. Destination from study this is for determine the right marketing strategy for increase sales and determine form alternative strategies based on Internal and External Appropriate Matrix and Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM) for applied to the coffee business. Result of study this about the form of strategy that will worn is the right marketing strategy for increase sales at XYZ coffee business using There are 4 SWOT matrix strategies, namely SO Strategy, WO, ST, and WT Strategy. Based on ranking on the TAS score , there are 8 alternative internal and external strategies Matrix , and the right Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM) for applied to the coffee business, namely follow as well as in on -site exhibition West Aceh tourism so that visitors from outside area so know XYZ coffee business, more creative in use technology so as not left behind in Thing promotion through social media, do innovation to product, maintain image or business image coffee for customers no reduce rather add new customer, repair location parking, give delivery order service, improve facility in effort for To do control product so on business Bakopi for goods could available and improve ability management and service so that consumers satisfied for shopping.

Keywords:- Coffee Business, SWOT Analysis, Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM).

I. INTRODUCTION

Coffee is one the most popular drink in the world, including in Indonesia. In Indonesia, coffee is commodity plantation cultivated people as source income and resources income foreign exchange. Even though Indonesia is not is a country with level largest coffee consumption, but Indonesia is one of the largest coffee producing countries. Indonesian coffee also has good quality, so many once people like type drink this. In the past, coffee was known as usual drink consumed parents, however now along with the more a lot variety of coffee, millennials also join competing enjoy drink one this. This thing take effect to level coffee consumption in Indonesia (Sidabalok , 2019).

The more increase coffee consumption, the more coffee many experience increase. This thing of course also supported by development technology in processing coffee to be more interesting for coffee lover, so cause increase amount businessman coffee shop. Besides have advantages, coffee of course also has a number of deficiency among them like identical coffee with a bitter taste and sour taste, quality election good coffee beans have acidity however with level low. The internal factors of coffee are like coffee variety, grade caffeine, levels acidity and water content (Triarko, et al, 2013).

Marketing strategy is a form pattern think about marketing that will used by business units for reach the goal. Marketing strategy also defines a target market and mix marketing related. This thing is something form description big from what will company apply in a number of the place business (Pasaribu , 2008).

XYZ Aceh 's coffee business is one of the manufacturers who sell packaged coffee powder having its address in West Aceh. XYZ coffee business has variation amount packaging and variations based on type Acehese specialty coffee powder, while for quality The coffee grounds offered are also varied start from the quality normal to the premium, the more tall quality coffee grounds of course the more low rate the caffeine that is owned and the taste is getting better favors. Coffee is one most popular drink Public from all among. See phenomenon development coffee business in Meulaboh with competitive competition moment this as well as happening The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in drop sale Aceh coffee powder in XYZ coffee business.

Method which used for prioritize strategy marketing that is SWOT analysis and QSPM (*Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix*). Profit with use QSPM matrix are strategies that can checked by sequentially and together, as well as no there is limit for amount strategy who can evaluated by at the same time (Zulkarnaen and Sutopo , 2013). QSPM evaluate attractiveness relatively from a number of choice alternative strategy objective (Bhandari and Verna, 2013). Use method SWOT (*Strength, Weaknesses, Threats, Opportunity*) and QSPM (*Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix*) for determine strategy company and develop model conceptual which appropriate in identifying the optimal area is very important for company strategy development next. In side other, analysis SWOT also could determine factors what which could help organization for reach goal and group

obstacles what just which dominate or must minimized for reach result that wanted (Pazouki , et al , 2017).

Study similar to that done by Efendi (2016) and Rizky (2019), with results study show alternative strategy which obtained from results processing data use Method QSPM (*Quantity Strategy Planning Matrix*) and matrix IFE and EFE, total score weight IFE as big as 1 and EFE as big as 0.99 put Shop Braderr Store is in quadrant XI (Stage start develop or still quiet customer), result rating priority strategy through QSPM, namely maintain image company , increase facility restaurant, defend quality and service product for interesting consumers, increase ability management and cooperation for destination company, give service *delivery* order for consumer, utilise progress technology for marketing , serve middle market share to lower with provide package or portion special, and guard connection good with supplier or the surrounding area restaurant .

Problem in study this is what is the best strategy applied to XYZ coffee business and how alternative strategy that must be prioritized in implementation in business that. So, author interested for To do study with title “Marketing Strategy Analysis Use SWOT and QSPM matrix in XYZ Aceh coffee business”.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

Study this carried out at the XYZ coffee business, which is located in Aceh Barat, Aceh, Indonesia. Type study this is study quantitative with explain and interpret something a phenomenon that occurs in a objects and data are quantitative i. e. data in the form of numbers and formulas according to category certain for get something conclusion. Study this conducted for knowing value of each variable, good one variable or more. On research this, author collect and observe circumstances that occur in XYZ's coffee business, so that study this is study qualitative. Study this started with studies field make something formulation problems and goals to be achieved from study this. Next, do studies literature related with topics raised in research this.

Stage data collection on research this includes primary data consisting of from observation or interaction ask answer with employee related condition workers and companies as well as problems and solutions solution and questionnaire that is with collect research instruments consisting of Suite question for gather information from party respondents. Meanwhile, the secondary data used namely sales data, sales targets, types of coffee grounds for sale, yield data sales and place XYZ coffee business.

Stages data processing is done with use SWOT method and *Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix* (QSPM) in four stage. Stage first is Step a formulation consisting of from *Internal Factor Evaluation* (IFE) seeks summarizing as well as evaluate strengths and weaknesses main in functions company, *External Factor Evaluation* (EFE) enables strategists to summarize and evaluate form opportunities and threats company. Stage second that is Step composing matrix *Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats* (SWOT Matrix) for determine the best strategy done by party company to become more focused and able made comparison from various angle. Next stages for position various divisions of a organization in something appearance nine column table that is with *Internal* and *External Matrix* (IE Matrix) and do QSPM analysis for evaluate various *alternative* strategies by objective, based on factors from level success from internal and external that have been identified before. Stage next Step data analysis and evaluation, namely the process of analyzing by detail and change results from processing data into a more information easy understandable and useful for solution there are problems in research.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

First steps taken in study this is gather results charging questionnaire from a number of source (owner stores, employees and consumers). Questionnaire used for data collection by the author is type questionnaire closed, where is the list of questions containing alternative the answer that has been provided by the author. Recapitulation results results deployment questionnaire could seen in Table 1 below.

No	Name Respondent	Answer Question Questionnaire																				Amount
		Opportunities				Treat				Strength								Weakness				
		O1	O2	O3	O4	T1	T2	T3	T4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	W1	W2	W3	W4	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20			
1	M. Rusli	2	5	4	5	5	5	4	4	5	5	5	4	3	4	3	3	4	4	5	5	84
2	Hamidah	3	2	4	5	4	2	3	4	2	4	3	3	5	5	4	4	2	4	5	2	70
3	Siti Sara	2	4	5	3	2	3	2	4	5	2	2	2	3	2	3	5	4	3	3	3	62
4	Zainal	4	2	5	2	5	5	5	3	2	2	4	3	3	4	5	5	4	3	2	2	70
5	Abdul	2	3	3	5	4	5	3	4	4	4	2	4	2	4	3	3	2	5	3	4	69
6	Usman B	5	5	2	2	3	5	5	2	2	3	2	3	2	4	2	3	3	2	3	5	63
7	Paradise	2	3	5	3	5	5	5	4	2	2	4	4	2	3	4	2	2	4	4	3	68
8	Usman	5	2	3	3	3	4	5	2	2	4	5	5	2	2	5	4	5	5	4	4	74
9	Nurhayati	5	5	5	5	2	2	4	3	3	5	4	3	3	3	4	3	4	3	3	3	72
10	Amri	2	5	3	4	5	2	5	4	3	5	4	3	3	5	5	5	5	3	5	2	78
11	Zainuddin	5	3	4	4	3	5	4	2	3	4	4	3	3	5	4	5	5	4	3	4	77

12	Salam	2	4	2	3	2	5	3	4	3	3	3	5	2	3	2	2	3	2	3	2	58
13	Rusdi	4	5	3	5	5	2	4	4	5	5	2	5	3	2	2	4	4	5	2	3	74
14	Saibah	5	4	3	3	3	2	5	2	4	4	2	5	2	5	2	3	3	2	2	4	65
15	Bustami	2	3	4	5	2	5	4	5	5	2	4	5	2	5	5	5	3	3	3	4	76
16	Nurmala	4	5	2	5	3	2	3	5	2	2	2	3	4	2	3	2	3	4	3	5	64
17	Imran	4	2	2	4	3	5	5	3	4	4	5	4	5	3	2	5	3	4	5	5	77
18	Idris	3	5	2	2	2	3	2	5	3	4	4	2	3	3	3	4	5	4	5	4	68
19	Jufri	2	4	4	4	4	2	3	5	3	5	5	4	2	2	4	5	3	2	3	5	71
20	Mulyono	2	5	4	2	3	4	3	4	4	3	4	3	5	2	2	2	3	4	5	5	69
Amount		65	76	69	74	68	73	77	73	66	72	70	73	59	68	67	74	70	70	71	74	1409
Total		28 4		29 1		54 9					28 5											

Table 1:- Recapitulation Results Questionnaire

Based on Table 1 above, recapitulation results deployment questionnaire have different answer every respondents. Form conversion answer respondent is in the form of a = 5, b = 4, c = 3, d = 2, and e = 1. Calculation amount for the number 1 question from good relationship _ with supplier ingredient raw with value 29, which is obtained of the total answers of 20 respondents namely: 2 + 3 + 2 + 4 + 2 + 5 + 2 + 5 + 5 + 2 + 5 + 2 + 4 + 5 + 2 + 4 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 2 = 65. Likewise using same way of calculation for question next.

Data processing with method weighting and grading EFE matrix, method weighting and grading IFE matrix, IE matrix (Internal - External), SWOT Matrix and QSPM Matrix (Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix).

Weighting and grading EFE matrix, done based on data collection from discussion with owner, power workers, and

consumers in the XYZ Aceh coffee business. After conducted discussion and giving questionnaire so generated weighting and rating assessment based on 4 questions for factor opportunity and 4 questions for factor threat for EFE matrix. Then, weighting and grading IFE (Internal Factor Evaluation) matrix, carried out based on data collection from company and discussion with owners, employees and consumers XYZ Aceh coffee business. After conducted discussion and giving questionnaire so generated weighting and rating ratings for IFE matrix.

From result gift data processing score weights on the IFE matrix and the EFE matrix, then the total weight x rating IFE is 3.49 and the total weight x rating is 3.60. Following this is the results of the total IE quadrant score are in Table 2 below.

Evaluation Factor Internal					
			Strong	Currently	Weak
		4.0	3.0	2.0	1.0
	Tall	3.0	I <i>Grow and Build</i>	II <i>Grow and Build</i>	III <i>Hold and Maintain</i>
Evaluation Factor External	Currently	2.0	IV <i>Grow and Build</i>	V <i>Hold and Maintain</i>	VI <i>Harvest or Divest</i>
	Low	1.0	VII <i>Hold and Maintain</i>	VIII <i>Harvest or Divest</i>	IX <i>Harvest or Divest</i>

Table 2:- Internal - External Matrix Total Score

B by results collection of questionnaire data obtained from XYZ Aceh coffee, as well as results discussion with owners and employees shop, then obtained strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. Strengths and Weaknesses is internal factors while opportunities and threats is factor external. Details SWOT matrix can be seen in Table 3 below.

ANALISIS SWOT	IFE	Strength (Strength)	Weakness (Weakness)
		1. Cooperation good fellow employee	1. Less spacious place for sale
		2. often have a promotion	
		3. Existence briefing and gift motivation before profession started	2. Sale which not yet can between address (Delivery)
		4. The place strategic business	
		5. Model the packaging variety and interesting	3. Lack of amount Employee Shop
		6. Service which good to consumer	
		7. Have a stock list for controlling ingredients raw	4. Area parking Not enough Large
EFE	8. Media social US means promotion		
Opportunity (Opportunities)	Strategy SO Combination S6–O4	Strategy WO Combination W4–O2	
1. Connection which good with suppliers ingredients raw	1. Improve facilities for XYZ Aceh coffee business Meulaboh so that could available storage ingredients raw.	1. Fix parking location for the sake of convenience consumers.	
2. Aceh West as citytour which often visited visitors for travel	2. More active in technology doing effort promotion approach to circle youth either directly or through social media.	2. Follow as well as in promotion in the place tour Aceh West so that visitors from outside area can know powder specialty coffee from XYZ Aceh coffee business .	
3. Style life circle young US lover coffee			
4. growing Technology			
Threat(Threats)	Strategy ST Combination S7–T4	Strategy WT Combination W2–T1	
1. Switching customers to competitors which kind of	1. Improve management skills and service so that consumer comfortable for shopping.	1. give service <i>Delivery Order</i> for consumers.	
2. Enter new competitors	2. Maintain satisfaction consumer to XYZ Aceh coffee business so that customers are not reduced, so they can add customer new.	2. do innovation to product with give discount.	
3. Rise price ingredients raw and supporters			
4. The rise product which innovative from competitors			

Table 3:- SWOT Matrix

From Table 3 above could be known that factor external and internal strategies obtained (SO), (WO), (ST), and (WT). Highest score on factor opportunity There are 2 strategies and strengths There are 2 strategies with score Lowest Threat 2 there are 2 strategies and weaknesses There are 2 strategies as following:

- Strengths and opportunities that is good service _ to consumers and development technology.
- Weaknesses and opportunities that is location less parking wide. Follow as well as in on site promotion West Aceh tourism so that visitors from outside area knowing special coffee powder from XYZ Aceh coffee.
- Strength and threat that is have a stock list for control ingredient raw. The rise product innovative from competitors.

- Weaknesses and threats that is sales not yet can between address (*Delivery Order*). entry competitor new.

Stage Taking decision that is with use QSPM matrix (*Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix*) which is something tool analysis for decide which strategy to use based on level attractiveness alternative strategies that exist.

In stages final in determine taking strategic decisions in enhancement sale XYZ Aceh coffee powder, where the EFE and IFE data are the reference data for analyze in take the best decision. Following results data processing with Method *Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix* (QSPM), can seen in Table 4 below this:

No	External Factor Evaluation (EFE)	Weight	Strategy	
			RATING	BAG
Opportunity				
1	Connection which good with suppliers ingredients raw	0.11	3	0.34
2	Aceh West US city the oftvisited visitors to travel	0.13	4	0.53
3	Style life among young as lover coffee	0.12	3	0.36
4	growing Technology	0.13	4	0.51
Total		0.49	14	1.74
No	External Factor Evaluation (EFE)	Weight	Strategy	
			RATING	BAG
Threat				
1	Switch it customer on competitors which kind of	0.12	3	0.35
2	Enter competitors new	0.13	4	0.51
3	Rise price ingredients raw and supporters	0.13	4	0.54
4	The rise product which innovative from competitors	0.13	4	0.51
Total		1.00	29	3.65
Total QSPM External Factor Evaluation (EFE)		1.49	43.00	5.39
No	Internal Factor Evaluation (IFE)	Weight	Strategy	
			RATING	BAG
Strength				
1	Cooperation which good fellow employee	0.08	3	0.24
2	often stage promotion	0.09	4	0.35
3	Existence briefing and gift motivation before profession started	0.08	4	0.34
4	The place the effort that strategic	0.09	4	0.35
5	Model packaging diverse and interesting	0.07	3	0.21
6	Service the good one to consumer	0.08	3	0.24
7	Have <i>List stock</i> for control ingredientsraw	0.08	3	0.24
8	Media social US promotional tools	0.09	4	0.35
Total		0.66	28	2.32
No	Internal Factor Evaluation (IFE)	Weight	Strategy	
			RATING	BAG
Weakness				
1	The place which not enough large for sale	0.08	4	0.34
2	Sale which not yet can between address (<i>Delivery</i>)	0.08	4	0.34
3	Lack of quantity Employee Shop	0.09	4	0.34
4	Area parking which less spacious	0.09	4	0.35
Total		1.00	44	3.69
Total QSPM Internal Factor Evaluation (IFE)		1.66	72	6.01

Table 4:- Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM)

Based on Table 4 above, then explanation about description results data processing with The QSPM method can understood on the details following:

- Calculation amount factor opportunity at number 1 good relationship _ with supplier ingredient raw obtained of the total answers of 20 respondents i. e. 5 + 2 + 5 + 2 + 4 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 3 + 5 + 4 + 5 + 2 + 4 + 3 + 3 + 4 = 66

- Calculation AS (Attractiveness Scores) an attractive score with how the total number of QSPM is divided with amount respondent 66: 20 = 3
- Calculation score weight taken on each factor External and Internal. On factor Opportunity, good relationship _ with supplier ingredient raw with score 0.11. On factor threat the switch customers to similar competitors _ with a score of 0.12 is taken on weight EFE data processing and

on IFE data processing factors strength, good cooperation between worker with score 0.08, and factor weakness less place _ large for sale with score 0.08

- Calculation for TAS EFE value on factor opportunity number 1 Good relationship with supplier ingredient raw obtained value (weight x AS) $0.11 \times 3 = 0.34$ so next on factor threats and IFE strengths and weaknesses.
- Result value weight On EFE (external Factor Evaluation of West Aceh 's opportunities as city frequent trips _ visited visitors for travel with TAS score 0.53 and progress technology with TAS score 0.51 While the factor

threat with score score Lowest entry competitor new with TAS score 0.51 and rampant product innovative from competitor with TAS score 0.51. Total calculation result with use EFE part QSPM method obtained through summation all data (Weight x US) then the total value of TAS in the EFE section is 3.65. Whereas for the total value of TAS in the IFE section is of 3.69.

From result data processing using The QSPM method can explained the strategy to be generated as following.

No	Alternative Strategy	Score BAG	Rating
1	Follow as well as in exhibition in the place tour pariaman so that visitors from outside area soknow XYZ Aceh coffee business	0.53	I
1	More creative in use technology so thatno left behind in Thing promotion through media social.	0.51	II
2	do innovation to product	0.51	III
3	Maintain image or image XYZ Aceh coffee business so that customer no reduce ratheradd customer which new.	0.35	IV
4	Repair location parking for the sake of convenience consumers.	0.34	V
5	Provide <i>Delivery Order</i> service for consumers.	0.34	VI
6	Improving facilities in an effort toto do control product so in XYZ Aceh coffee business so that goods could available.	0.24	VII
7	Improve management skills service so that consumers are satisfied for shopping.	0.24	VIII

Table 5:- Alternative appropriate strategy _ ranking on the TAS . score

Based on Table 5. above, then explanation about alternative strategy ranking with QSPM methods are:

- West Aceh as city frequent trips visited visitors for travel with TAS score 0.53 with follow up strategy as well as in on -site exhibition tour pariaman so that visitors from outside area so know XYZ Aceh coffee business.
- growing technology with TAS score 0.51 with strategy results in the form of more creative in use technology so as not left behind in Thing promotion through social media.
- The rise product innovative from competitor with TAS score 0.51 with strategy results innovation to product.
- While the factor threat with score score Lowest the switch customers to similar competitors with TAS score 0.35 with results of the defense strategy image or XYZ Aceh coffee business imageso that customers no reduce rather add new customer.
- Less parking area large with TAS score 0.34 with strategy results improve location parking for convenience consumers.
- While the factor weakness with score lowest, Sales yet can between Delivery Order address with TAS score 0.34 with strategy results provide Delivery Order service for consumers.

- Have a stock list for control product so with TAS score 0.24 with Strategy results Improve facility in effort for To do control product so at the XYZ Aceh coffee business order goods could available.
- Good service to consumer with TAS score 0.24 with Strategy results Improve ability management and service so that consumers satisfied for shopping.

Next results analysis for each EFE matrix and IFE matrix .

➤ *Analysis EFE Matrix*

Result of identification The EFE (External Factor Evaluation) matrix is : opportunities and threats that affect XYZ Aceh 's coffee business. On factor highest chance is Aceh Barat as city frequent trips visited visitors for travel obtained score by 0.53 and growing Technology with score 0.51. Factors that have opportunity positive the must utilized as good as maybe by XYZ Aceh coffee business. From the EFE matrix above, it can also be seen factor threat Lowest for XYZ Aceh coffee business that is Switch it customers to competitors kind of with score 0.35. Factors that have threat negative the must fixed by XYZ Aceh coffee with method utilise factor opportunity. The result of the total multiplication between weighting and rating assessment will be produce total value with score of 3.60.

➤ Analysis IFE Matrix

IFE (Internal Factor Evaluation) Matrix in study this containing about internal factors of XYZ Aceh coffee. These internal factors cover strength (strength) which is factor positive for company and the weaknesses (weaknesses) which are factor negative for effort that. Factors this got from data collection, then each of these factor weight x rating. Based on IFE matrix is Factor the power that has score the highest one is social media as means promotion 0.35 and Place strategic business with score 0.35. Factors strength have role positive the must utilized as good as maybe by XYZ Aceh coffee From the IFE matrix above it can also be seen factor weakness biggest for XYZ Aceh coffee, the parking area is lacking large with score 0.33 and Sales that have not can between address (Delivery Order) with score 0.29. The result of the total multiplication between weighting and rating assessment will be resulting in a total score of 3.49. Factor weakness the must be repaired XYZ Aceh coffee with utilise factor existing power.

Next, analyze results IE Matrix and SWOT Matrix data processing for XYZ Aceh coffee. Description about Step analysis for IE Matrix and SWOT Matrix can be look at the explanation following:

➤ IE Matrix

Based on results from IFE matrix and EFE matrix then could arranged next in IE matrix obtained an average IFE value of 3.49 and an average EFE of 3.60. Based on from results data processing performed that fall on point quadrant I shows level XYZ Aceh coffee sales belong to the Grow and Build category, the strategy used is development packaging products and upgrades market share.

➤ SWOT Matrix

SWOT matrix contains strategies for minimize lack of XYZ Aceh coffee and avoid factor existing threats. The results of data collection in the form of questionnaire and results discussion with owner business, employees, and consumers at XYZ Aceh coffee writer get results in the form of 8 priority strategies table SWOT matrix, namely :

• SO Strategy

Increase XYZ Aceh coffee facilities so that goods could available with score 0.24 more active in technology so as not left behind in Thing promotion especially for social media with score 0.51.

• WO Strategy

Repair location parking for convenience consumer a score of 0.34 and the Aceh Barat factor as city frequent trips visited visitors for travel could knowing XYZ Aceh specialty coffee powder with score 0.53.

• ST strategy

Increase ability management and service so that consumers satisfied for shopping with score 0.24. Maintain image or XYZ Aceh coffee business imageso that customers no switch to competitors who have product kind of with score 0.35.

• WT Strategy

Give Delivery Order service for consumer with score 0.34 and Do innovation to product with score 0.51.

Then, step next taking decision. At stage this containing about analysis results processing data from QSPM Matrix (Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix). QSPM Matrix Results are taken from The SWOT matrix gets the strategy that will used in XYZ Aceh's coffee business is for enhancement sale with description as following:

➤ On EFE (External Factor Evaluation) seen on the factors opportunity highest namely : Aceh Barat as city frequent trips _ visited visitors for travel could knowing special coffee powder XYZ Aceh coffee business with TAS score 0.53 with strategy results Follow as well as in on -site exhibition West Aceh tourism so that visitors from outside knowing special coffee powder XYZ Aceh coffee business and its development technology with TAS score 0.51 with More strategy results active in technology so as not left behind in Thing promotion especially for social media. While the factor threat with score score Lowest the switch customers to similar competitors with TAS score 0.35 with Defend strategy results image or an image of the XYZ Aceh coffee business so that you can add new and booming customers product innovative from competitor with TAS score 0.51 with strategy results Perform innovation to product. from results calculation with using QSPM, the total value of TAS in the EFE section is 3.65.

➤ On IFE (Internal Factor Evaluation) seen on the factors strength with score highest that is The place strategic business with TAS score 0.35 with strategy results improve ability management and service so that consumers satisfied for shopping and have a stock list for control product so with TAS score 0.24 with strategy results improve facility XYZ Aceh coffee business so that goods could available. While the factor weakness with score lowest, Sales yet can between Delivery Order address with TAS score 0.34 with Strategy results Deliver Delivery Order service for consumers and less parking area large with TAS score 0.34 with Strategy result Fix location parking for convenience consumers. from calculation result with using QSPM, the total value of TAS in the IFE section is 3.69.

IV. CONCLUSION

The results of data processing and analysis show the strategies that will used in the XYZ Aceh coffee business, namely the right marketing strategy for increase sales at XYZ Aceh coffee business using There are 4 strategies in the SWOT matrix, namely: SO Strategy which is a combination between S6 good service to consumer and O4 development technology. Then, the WO strategy which is combination between W4 parking area not enough area and O2 Aceh Barat as frequent city visited visitors for travel, ST strategy which is combination between S7 social media as means promotions and T4 are rampant innovative product from competitors, WT strategy which is combination between W2 Sales that have not can between address (Delivery Order) and T1 switch customers to similar competitors. Based on ranking on the TAS score, there are 8 alternative strategies based on Internal

and External Matrix, and the right Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM) for applied to the XYZ Aceh coffee business, namely follow as well as in on -site exhibition West Aceh tourism so that visitors from outside area so know XYZ Aceh coffee business, with TAS score of 0.53, more creative in use technology so as not left behind in Thing promotion through social media, with TAS score of 0.51, doing innovation to product, with TAS score of 0.51 and maintain image or image of XYZ Aceh coffee business so that customers no reduce rather add new customer, with TAS score of 0.35, improving location parking for convenience consumers, with TAS score of 0.34, giving Delivery Order service for consumers, with TAS score of 0.34, increase facility in effort for To do control product so at the XYZ Aceh coffee business so that goods could available, with TAS score of 0.24 and increase ability management and service so that consumers satisfied for shopping, with TAS score of 0.24

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